

Applying Gagné and Medsker's Instructional Model in Organizing Career Guidance Activities for Lower Secondary School Students

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ABSTRACT: Career guidance is a compulsory component at the lower secondary level, supporting the reform goals of the General Education Curriculum with a focus on competency-based development. It is implemented through three main formats: flag-raising sessions, homeroom activities, and thematic educational activities. This study examines the processes of knowledge acquisition and competency formation based on the instructional framework of Gagné and Medsker. By analyzing how learners receive and apply knowledge within this model, the paper provides a theoretical basis for improving instructional design in career guidance. Based on these findings, the study proposes applying Gagné and Medsker's instructional process to the design of career guidance lessons for lower secondary students. This approach ensures alignment with the curriculum's content, characteristics, and objectives, thereby enhancing the effectiveness of career guidance activities in developing students' competencies and supporting their career orientation.

KEYWORDS: Career education, middle school students, teaching organization, teaching process, career exploration

I. INTRODUCTION

In the context of globalization and the rapid advancement of science and technology, particularly the Fourth Industrial Revolution, general education is facing an urgent need for substantial reform to meet the demands for high-quality human resources. One of the key directions in contemporary education is the shift from a content-based approach to a competency-based approach, emphasizing the development of learners' qualities and competencies. Among these, career orientation competence has been identified as a core competency that students need to develop (Ministry of Education and Training, 2018). For lower secondary school students—a critical stage for developing self-awareness and future orientation—career guidance activities play a significant role in helping them explore their abilities, personal interests, and make initial career-related decisions (Thoa, 2020). However, the current implementation of career guidance education in lower secondary schools still reveals several limitations. Career guidance activities are often limited to information delivery, lacking systematic organization and insufficiently integrated with the teaching process. Instructional methods remain monotonous and fail to promote students' active engagement and autonomy. Additionally, the design of these activities is not consistently grounded in scientific pedagogical frameworks, resulting in limited educational effectiveness (Đà, 2023; Le, 2024). Consequently, students encounter difficulties in self-awareness, lack decision-making skills related to career choices, and are inadequately prepared for future educational pathways (Savickas, 2013; McWhirter, 2020).

In this context, the application of modern instructional models and frameworks to career guidance education becomes essential. One such model with strong theoretical and practical value is the instructional model proposed by Gagné and Medsker. According to Gagné and Medsker instruction should be designed as a sequence of instructional events aimed at stimulating and supporting learners' cognitive processes. This model consists of nine key steps: gaining attention, informing learners of objectives, stimulating recall of prior knowledge, presenting new content, providing learning guidance, eliciting performance, providing feedback, assessing performance, and enhancing retention and transfer. Each step corresponds to internal cognitive processes, thereby ensuring alignment between teaching and learning activities (Gagné and Medsker, 1996; Jordan, 2008).

A notable strength of the Gagné and Medsker instructional model lies in its systematic and logical structure, as well as its capacity to regulate the learning process effectively. This model not only enables teachers to organize instruction in a scientific manner but also facilitates active learner engagement, supporting the gradual and sustainable development of knowledge and skills. Previous studies in instructional design have demonstrated that applying Gagné's model contributes to improved learning outcomes, particularly in developing practical skills and competencies (Gagné, Wager, Golas, & Keller, 2005).

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In the context of career guidance education, the application of the Gagné and Medsker model is particularly meaningful. Career guidance is not merely about providing occupational information; rather, it involves organizing learning experiences that enable students to explore, reflect, and make informed decisions. Therefore, a clear pedagogical framework is necessary to ensure the effectiveness of such activities. The application of Gagné’s nine instructional events allows teachers to design career guidance activities in a logical sequence aligned with students’ cognitive characteristics—from capturing initial interest and providing occupational information to organizing experiential learning and evaluating students’ understanding (Gagné & Medsker , 1996; Jordan, 2008).

Moreover, this model enhances the integration between teaching and career guidance, facilitating the incorporation of career education into subject teaching and school-based educational activities. Through instructional activities structured according to Gagné’s model, students not only acquire knowledge but also actively participate in practice, receive feedback, and engage in self-assessment. This process contributes to the development of self-awareness and career decision-making competencies, which are essential in modern society.

Based on the aforementioned considerations, investigating the application of Gagné and Medsker’s instructional model in organizing career guidance activities for lower secondary school students is both necessary and significant in terms of theory and practice. This study is expected to contribute to the theoretical foundation of designing career guidance activities based on scientific instructional models, as well as to propose practical solutions for improving the effectiveness of career guidance education in schools, thereby meeting the demands of educational reform in the current context.

II. GAGNÉ AND MEDSKER’S INSTRUCTIONAL PROCESS

In the instructional process, the teacher’s role is manifested in designing and organizing instructional stimuli in a purposeful manner, enabling learners to respond in accordance with predetermined learning objectives and thereby facilitating the formation of desired behaviors. Gagné and Medsker proposed a nine-step instructional process in which teachers’ actions are systematically aligned with corresponding learner responses. This alignment ensures coherence between teaching and learning activities, contributing to the effectiveness of the instructional process (Gagné & Medsker , 1996; Jordan, 2008).

Figure 1. The teacher’s instructional process.

Figure 1 illustrates the nine-step instructional process proposed by Gagné and Medsker, which provides a systematic framework for optimizing learning by establishing a scientific instructional sequence in which each teaching action is designed to elicit corresponding cognitive and psychological responses from learners (Gagné & Medsker, 1996; Jordan, 2008). This process enhances learning effectiveness through four interrelated phases.

Steps one to three represent the preparatory and orientation phase, ensuring that learners are cognitively and motivationally ready to engage in the learning process. Gaining learners’ attention initiates engagement through appropriate stimuli, while clearly stating learning objectives helps learners focus their efforts on specific goals. At the same time, activating prior knowledge stimulates existing cognitive structures, enabling learners to connect new information with previously acquired knowledge (Gagné & Medsker, 1996; Jordan, 2008).

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Steps four to five constitute the information presentation and processing phase, which forms the core of new knowledge acquisition. Emphasizing key content directs learners’ attention to essential information, thereby reducing cognitive load. Presenting the learning structure further supports comprehension by organizing content into a coherent system, allowing learners to recognize relationships among different components of the lesson (Gagné & Medsker, 1996; Jordan, 2008).

Steps six to seven correspond to the practice and feedback phase, promoting active learning through interaction and performance. Organizing learning activities encourages learners to express their understanding, thereby enhancing retention and deepening comprehension. Providing timely feedback enables learners to regulate their learning processes, reinforce correct responses, and improve learning motivation (Gagné & Medsker, 1996; Jordan, 2008).

Finally, steps eight and nine represent the transfer phase, ensuring learners achieve mastery and long-term retention. Assessing learning outcomes helps determine the extent to which learning objectives have been achieved, while consolidation and generalization activities facilitate the integration and transfer of knowledge. This phase also prepares learners for subsequent learning cycles, thereby maintaining the continuity of the instructional process (Gagné & Medsker, 1996; Jordan, 2008).

III. THE ROLE OF CAREER COUNSELING IN LOWER SECONDARY EDUCATION

Self-exploration and career identity development: Career guidance counseling helps students develop a clear understanding of their interests, abilities, personal values, and corresponding career orientations, thereby fostering a stable career identity. A study conducted in vocational schools in Indonesia indicates that career counseling services play a significant role in supporting students in developing their career identity, reducing confusion in major selection, and better preparing them for the future (Karim & Sa’adah, 2021).

Soft skills development: Research shows that career guidance interventions have a positive impact on soft skills such as leadership and communication, while also enhancing students’ confidence and adaptability in future work environments (Nur Inyatun Nisa, 2025).

Career adaptability development: Theory-based interventions have been demonstrated to enhance career adaptability, including competencies related to concern, control, and confidence in future career pathways (Bersan et al., 2024).

Personal planning and career goal-setting skills: Career guidance counseling supports students in developing personalized career plans, including short-, medium-, and long-term goals aligned with their abilities and aspirations. Activities such as group counseling, mock interviews, and the use of career mapping tools help students establish clear and feasible career orientations (St Martin’s School, 2024).

Figure 1. Six Holland personality types.

The core content of John Holland’s six personality–career types is presented as follows (Hò & Trần, 2011):

- **Realistic:** This group shows a preference for activities that involve working with objects, tools, machines, and animals in a clear, orderly, and systematic manner. However, individuals in this group tend to have less interest in educational or therapeutic activities.

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- **Investigative:** This group typically prefers activities that require inquiry and curiosity in fields such as physics, biology, and culture. Individuals in this group tend to have less interest in persuasive or communicative activities.
- **Artistic:** This group tends to favor free and creative activities. They generally show less preference for structured, systematic, or rule-based tasks.
- **Social:** Individuals in the Social group prefer activities that involve working with others, including education, support, and helping roles. They tend to have less interest in technical, structured, or system-based activities involving materials, tools, or machines.
- **Enterprising:** This group prefers activities that involve influencing and leading others to achieve organizational or personal goals, often related to economic benefits. They tend to have less interest in observational, symbolic, or highly structured activities.
- **Conventional:** This group prefers activities that involve handling data in a clear, orderly, and systematic manner. They tend to have less interest in ambiguous, unstructured, exploratory, or non-systematic activities.

IV. THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS FOR ORGANIZING CAREER GUIDANCE ACTIVITIES FOR LOWER SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN VIETNAM

A. Objective

“Career guidance activities help students gain an understanding of several occupational fields, develop awareness in cultivating essential qualities of the workforce, and formulate appropriate learning and training plans aligned with their career orientation upon completing the stage of basic education” (Ministry of Education and Training, 2018).

B. Content of organizing career guidance activities in lower secondary education

Career guidance activities focus on the self, including self-exploration and self-development, as well as exploration of occupations. Occupational exploration activities may involve understanding the meaning and characteristics of different career fields, developing qualities and competencies aligned with career orientation, selecting appropriate career pathways, and formulating learning plans consistent with career goals (Ministry of Education and Training, 2018).

C. Forms of organizing career guidance activities

Flag-raising assembly: The implementation of flag-raising sessions is typically structured into two parts. The first part consists of school rituals and administrative activities. The second part involves classes taking turns to organize or present activities based on specific educational themes.

Class meetings: The implementation of class meetings may be organized as follows. The first part focuses on class administration, including weekly reviews of class activities, commendations, reminders for students, and preparation for upcoming weekly and monthly activities. The second part involves groups or teams taking turns to organize or present activities aligned with educational themes.

Thematic educational activities: These are conducted regularly on a weekly basis through various forms such as club activities, games, forums, interactive theater, field trips, excursions, competitions, exchange activities, campaign-based activities, humanitarian activities, volunteer work, community service, and collective activities (Ministry of Education and Training, 2018; Thoa, 2020).

D. Process of organizing career guidance activities

- Based on the experiential encoding process of learners (H1), the nine-step instructional design process of Gagné and Medsker (Table 2), and the experiential learning model that explains how learners construct experience, the author proposes a nine-step process for organizing experiential and career guidance activities for lower secondary school students as follows:
- **Step 1:** Organize activities to elicit students' prior experiences related to the skills to be developed. Various methods such as questionnaires, questioning, and short games can be used to enhance students' engagement.
- **Step 2:** Based on students' prior experiences and the expected knowledge and skills, determine the level of learner behavior according to Bloom's taxonomy.
- **Step 3:** Provide learning experiences for students through different forms of educational activities, selecting either direct (primary) or indirect (secondary) experiences in alignment with the instructional objectives.
- **Step 4:** Organize activities that enable learners to describe what occurred during their participation in the experience.
- **Step 5:** Facilitate activities that allow students to process their experiences based on the descriptions generated in Step 4.
- **Step 6:** Organize activities that encourage students to reflect on how they processed the experience and the outcomes obtained.
- **Step 7:** Provide opportunities for students to demonstrate the knowledge gained through experience and reflection, and to identify the knowledge and skills needed to address similar situations.

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- Step 8: Organize activities to assess learners’ responses and compare them with their initial experiences, thereby supporting the formation of new experiences.
- Step 9: Consolidate and generalize the learning content, and provide guidance for subsequent learning activities.

The process of organizing experiential activities consists of nine steps. At each step, teachers apply relevant theoretical foundations in instructional design, including forms of experiential learning organization, active teaching methods, educational approaches, and the formulation of learning objectives using action verbs aligned with Bloom’s taxonomy, thereby facilitating the assessment of students’ competencies at each level.

Example of organizing a career guidance activity for lower secondary school students

Topic: Career Exploration

Activity: Experiential Career Guidance Activity

Objective of the activity: The activity aims to help students understand occupational diversity, explore personal strengths and interests, develop career-related competencies, and form initial career orientations aligned with their future learning pathways.

Table 1. Career Guidance Activity Plan

Instructional Steps (Gagné)	Learning Outcomes (Career Competency-Oriented)	Teacher Activities	Student Activities
1. Gain attention	Students demonstrate initial awareness of the diversity of occupations and develop interest in career exploration.	The teacher presents a short video illustrating various occupations and poses eliciting questions to stimulate curiosity and engagement.	Students observe the video and respond to guiding questions, sharing initial perceptions of preferred occupations.
2. State objectives	Students identify and understand the learning objectives related to occupational exploration.	The teacher explicitly states lesson objectives, including understanding occupational concepts, classification, and personal relevance.	Students listen and articulate the expected learning outcomes.
3. Elicit prior knowledge	Students activate prior knowledge and experiences related to occupations in real-life contexts.	The teacher asks prompting questions about familiar occupations and their characteristics.	Students recall and share existing knowledge and experiences.
4. Present content	Students explain the concept of occupation and classify basic occupational groups.	The teacher delivers structured content on occupational definitions, classifications, and representative examples.	Students listen, take notes, and engage in clarification questions.
5. Provide guidance	Students apply strategies to explore information about a specific occupation (e.g., tasks, requirements, opportunities).	The teacher organizes group work, provides worksheets, and scaffolds the information-seeking process.	Students collaborate in groups to collect, analyze, and synthesize occupational information.
6. Elicit performance	Students present findings on a selected occupation in a structured manner.	The teacher facilitates group presentations and ensures equal participation.	Students present group outcomes and respond to peer questions.
7. Provide feedback	Students refine and consolidate their understanding of occupations based on feedback.	The teacher provides constructive feedback, clarifies misconceptions, and extends key ideas.	Students receive feedback and adjust their understanding accordingly.
8. Assess performance	Students evaluate their level of understanding and achievement in occupational exploration.	The teacher conducts formative assessment through questioning and evaluation criteria.	Students respond to assessment tasks and engage in self- and peer-assessment.
9. Enhance retention and transfer	Students relate occupational knowledge to personal orientation and propose initial career intentions.	The teacher summarizes key content and assigns transfer tasks related to personal career planning.	Students reflect on personal interests and identify potential career pathways.

Table 1 presents a plan for organizing career guidance activities for middle school students focusing on career exploration, structured according to Gagné’s Nine Teaching Steps. This table systematizes the guidance steps with competency-oriented learning outcomes, as well as the corresponding activities of teachers and students. This linkage ensures a coherent guidance flow, in which each pedagogical action is purposefully linked to specific cognitive and behavioral responses of the learners.

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V. CONCLUSION

The ongoing reform of the general education curriculum toward a competency-based approach places particular emphasis on the organization of career guidance activities for lower secondary school students. To fully realize the role of teachers and the nature of the learning process in designing effective career guidance activities, this study has clarified the theoretical foundations and proposed an approach for applying Gagné and Medsker's instructional model in this context.

By structuring instructional activities according to a nine-step process, the study contributes to systematizing the organization of career guidance activities in a scientific, logical, and competency-oriented manner. The findings indicate that integrating this model not only enhances the structural coherence of instructional activities but also promotes students' active participation, self-awareness, and career orientation.

However, the present study is primarily limited to theoretical analysis and instructional design. Therefore, future research should incorporate empirical studies with more diverse samples and contexts to validate the effectiveness of the proposed model in educational practice. The integration of both qualitative and quantitative approaches is expected to provide more robust scientific evidence, thereby improving the feasibility and applicability of Gagné and Medsker's instructional model in career guidance education at the lower secondary level.

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